

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CANONICAL NSGA-II AND NSGA-II-HHO FOR POWER DISTRIBUTION CONDUCTOR ALLOCATION

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Abstract

The potential of hybridizing Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) with Harris Hawks Optimization (HHO) algorithm remains largely unexplored, especially for distribution feeder planning problems; thereby leaving a research gap to be filled. This article therefore investigates the aspects of performance improvement when the NSGA-II is hybridized with HHO algorithm, for multi-objective distribution system planning. Both algorithms (NSGA-II and NSGA-II-HHO) were deployed on the IEEE 33-bus feeder with no DG under the same load-flow and cost models, with equal computational budgets. Each was executed independently for 20 runs, and results were collated across three representative loading scenarios, with three conductor types. Performance was evaluated using convergence/divergence metrics, Pareto quality metrics, and statistical significance testing via Mann-Whitney U test. Results indicate that NSGA-II-HHO achieves a 43.59% reduction in IGD+ relative to NSGA-II ($p = 0.021$, $r = 0.43$), indicating significantly improved convergence to the true Pareto front. However, runtime was 9.46% higher for the hybrid; with a moderate effect size ($r = -0.34$) and a meaningful median difference, this increase was however not statistically significant ($p = 0.072$). All other metrics recorded statistically insignificant improvement i.e., no proven loss in diversity. Smoother convergence and reduced run-to-run variability, particularly around the critical cost/loss knee region, were also observed. The modest rise in runtime and mean conductor capital cost are arguably acceptable trade-offs for the hybrid's better convergence and reliability. Overall, the study provides comparative results from a verifiable multi-objective optimization framework for the optimal assignment of conductors in the test case and similar network topologies – setting the foundation for future results in multi-scenario, large scale and high dimensional deployments of the algorithms.

Keywords: Conductor Allocation, Distribution Systems, Harris Hawks Optimization (HHO), Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II), Mixed-Integer Non-Linear Programming (MINLP), Multi-objective optimization problem (MOOP).

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The rising focus on financial cost and efficiency optimization in distribution network design derives from the need for reliable, scalable, and economically

sustainable power systems. Utilities have continued to employ advanced planning models and optimization algorithms to minimize capital expenses (CAPEX) and operational expenses (OPEX), improve voltage

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stability, and crash power losses (Hemeida *et al.*, 2023). Multi-objective optimization, especially through metaheuristic and hybrid algorithms, is commonly used for conductor right-sizing, topology reconfiguration, and asset management; to strike an optimal balance between technical and economic objectives (Obakpolor *et al.*, 2024). This trend portrays a broader shift toward intelligent, cost-effective feeder planning in response to dynamic energy and regulatory demands (Thein *et al.*, 2022).

Conductor selection/allocation plays a cardinal role in determining both capital and operational costs. While large gauge conductors connote higher investment, they reduce joule losses and enhance voltage regulation; conversely, smaller gauge conductors lower upfront costs but increase energy losses over the feeder's useful life (Kolobov *et al.*, 2024). Since energy losses in distribution feeders can represent a substantial share of the OPEX, an optimal trade-off between conductor upfront cost and the cost of resistive losses is necessary. (Sadiq, & Antar, 2024). This trade-off naturally forms a multi-objective optimization problem (MOOP) with no single global optimum, but a Pareto set of the best cost-performance trade-offs. Metaheuristic algorithms are notably suitable for this task, as they effectively approximate the Pareto front and present feeder planners with various near-optimal design options (Mishra *et al.*, 2022).

2.0 Literature Review

Many recent studies have employed hybrid metaheuristics to handle MOOP in radial distribution networks, concentrating on tasks such as distributed generation (DG) and Soft Open Point (SOP) placements (Abdo *et al.*, 2025). A hybrid Whale Optimization Algorithm/Particle Swarm Optimization (WOA/PSO) has been used to handle the mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP) characteristics of DG and SOP allocation (Baran & Wu, 1989; Gad, 2022). Similarly, an Arithmetic-Salp Swarm Optimizer hybrid has been used to reduce joule losses and annual financial expenses through multi-DG allocation (Hasan *et al.*, 2025) while an adaptive Differential Evolution/PSO hybrid improved convergence speed and computational efficiency for DG sizing and placement (Singh & Kumar, 2025). Beyond allocation, hybrid metaheuristics have been deployed in network topology reconfiguration, where a Genetic Algorithm/Harmony Search Algorithm

(GA-HSA) achieved superior performance by integrating GA's exploration with HSA's local search (Hamadneh *et al.*, 2025), and a Particle Swarm Optimization-Gravitational Search Algorithm (PSO-GSA) achieved both DG allocation and network reconfiguration simultaneously, with improved voltage regulation and reduced total losses (Nagamora *et al.*, 2022; Najm *et al.*, 2024).

Related studies confirm that hybrid HHO algorithms have been successfully deployed to a wide range of multi-objective power system problems. These hybrids consistently outperform baseline HHO and single-algorithm approaches, particularly in high-dimensional, and MOOP settings where the exploration-exploitation tradeoff is most critical. (Nazari & Abdi 2023, Gnana Malar *et al.*, 2024, Liu *et al.*, 2025, Upputuri *et al.*, 2024)

A few efforts have also been made to benchmark and develop hybrid HHO variants for power system applications; integrating adaptive mechanisms, elite preservation, cross-algorithmic hybridization and chaotic dynamics. On engineering design problems, HHO-Elite and HHO-PSO achieved up to 35% faster convergence than baseline HHO, besides very low variance for most hybrids. (Sharma, *et al.*, 2025)

Meanwhile, the relatively recent Harris Hawks Optimization (HHO) algorithm has displayed high efficiency in continuous optimization, and its hybrids with Differential Evolution and the Sine-Cosine Algorithm have achieved superior convergence and diversity in optimal power flow and engineering design problems (Abd Elaziz *et al.*, 2021).

None of the foregoing has methodologically developed a hybrid framework comprising the NSGA-II and the HHO (NSGA-II-HHO); to unveil likely performance differences with the baseline

This study seeks to answer the research question i.e., compared to the canonical baseline (NSGA-II), does the hybridization of HHO with NSGA-II drive any significant mechanistic improvement in convergence and/or diversity when deployed on a MOOP radial distribution feeder planning problem? The NSGA-II's global search, together with the HHO's adaptive behavior deserves some systematic investigation.

This study therefore aims to fill this key gap in power distribution system planning and optimization research by conducting a rigorous assessment of the likely impact of hybridizing NSGA-II with HHO for

the simultaneous optimization of system efficiency and capital investment cost in a radial distribution feeder test case.

3.0 Materials and Methods

The workflow was designed to permit each algorithm to optimally allocate three different conductor types along the distribution feeder while enforcing fairness and reproducibility in the comparative performance evaluation of NSGA-II and NSGA-II-HHO. Both algorithms were deployed on the IEEE 33-bus distribution feeder (Baran & Wu, 1989) under identical experimental conditions. To mitigate stochasticity, each algorithm was deployed for 20 runs with different random seeds, and performance metrics were aggregated across runs. With three representative loading scenarios, solutions were evaluated using a weighted fitness function to mimic realistic demand variations across typical operating conditions; thus, balancing realism and computational efficiency. Key demand variations are thereby captured to yield robust solutions under typical operating conditions, without the high cost of full stochastic methods. The selected scenarios and weights follow standard distribution system practice, reflecting typical load patterns across the demand range (Li *et al.*, 2022; Schneider & Fuller 2010). Comparative performance was evaluated using divergence, convergence and Pareto quality metrics, while statistical significance was verified via Mann-Whitney U test on the aggregated outcomes.

3.1 Power system description

A steady-state operational framework under realistic techno-economic constraints was adopted. Three commercially available Aluminum Conductor Steel Reinforced (ACSR) types (1/0, 2/0, and 3/0) were modeled using a fixed-parameter π -equivalent representation, neglecting temperature dependencies for computational simplicity. CAPEX covered only material costs. Loads were modeled as constant power (PQ) elements with residential, commercial, and industrial diversity, while benchmark base loads were scaled using customer-type multipliers to reflect daily variations and seasonality. The substation voltage was fixed at 1.00 p.u., with no auxiliary voltage regulation. This modeling framework aligns with established patterns in prior studies (Mishra, Das, & Paul, 2022; IEEE PES Test Feeder Working Group, 2022; Nayeripour *et al.*, 2013).

In line with widespread practices among many Sub-Saharan African utilities, where feeder planners major

on grid expansion and cost/loss trade-offs, with little or no consideration of distributed generation due to diverse constraints (International Energy Agency, 2022); the test system was modeled without renewable energy footprint. This simplification reflects baseline feeder planning conditions in many regions of the world.

3.2 Problem formulation

To represent the problem's objectives and constraints, it was formulated as a bi-objective MINLP model:

$$\text{Minimize: } F(x) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x) \\ f_2(x) \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{Pareto optimality}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } C_j(x) \leq 0, \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, 5 \quad (2)$$

$$x^L \leq x \leq x^U \quad (3)$$

where $f_1(x)$ denotes the total joule losses, $f_2(x)$ denotes the total CAPEX of conductors, and $C_1 - C_5$ enforce network and operational constraints.

$x = (x_i, x_j)$ stands for the decision vector, bounded such that $x^L \leq x \leq x^U$, where x^L and x^U denote the lower and upper bounds respectively. $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the continuous variables (system operating states) and $x_j \in \mathbb{Z}^m$ are the discrete variables (design decisions). The following subsections outline more detail and describes the mathematical expressions for the optimization problem.

3.2.1 Decision variables

The decision variables are the conductor types assigned to the feeder segments.

$$x_i \in \{1, 2, 3\}, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

Where x_i denotes the conductor type assigned to line segment i .

N_i is the number of distribution line conductors = 32.

Each candidate conductor configuration was evaluated across three representative demand scenarios (peak, average, and light load) with type-specific and seasonal multipliers to capture diverse operating conditions. The weighted average of scenario losses was used as the technical performance indicator in the optimization process.

3.2.2 Objective functions

Minimization of active power losses:

$$\text{Minimize: } f_1(x) = \sum_{s \in S} w_s P_{loss}^s(x)$$

Minimization of total conductor capital cost.

Minimize: $f_2(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_l} C_{x_i} \cdot L_{i-j}$ Where, $S = \{\text{Peak, Average, Light}\}$ represents operating scenarios with weights (Fang, Mu, Liu, & Yang, 2024; Choobdari, Samiei Moghaddam, Davarzani, Azarfar, & Hoseinpour, 2024) as follows:

$$w_{peak} = w_{Average} = 0.4 \text{ and } w_{Light} = 0.2$$

$P_{loss}^s(x)$ denotes the system active power loss in (MW) under conductor assignment x in scenario s

C_{x_i} denotes the cost per km of conductor type x_i

L_{i-j} denotes the length of line segment $i - j$

3.2.3 Constraints

C_1 : Budget constraints

$$f_3(x) \leq B_{max} \tag{7}$$

Where, the upper limit for the conductor CAPEX $B_{max} = \$40,000$

C_2 : Real and reactive power balance

$$f_4(x) = 0 \tag{8}$$

where $f_4(x)$ represents both active and reactive power balance equations

C_4 : per unit voltage constraints

$$0.95 \leq V_i \leq 1.05 \quad \forall_i \in n \tag{9}$$

C_5 : Thermal constraints

$$I_i(x) = 0.8 I_i^{max}(x_i), \quad \forall_i \in n \tag{10}$$

Where, $I_i(x)$ is the current in line i under assignment x , and $I_i^{max}(x_i)$ is the thermal rating of the selected conductor.

3.3 Constraint violation handling

Constraint violations were managed using penalty functions integrated into the objective evaluation (García-Nieto & Alba, 2022):

$$\text{Budget violation: } e_{budget} = \frac{f_2(x) - B_{max}}{B_{max}} \cdot \alpha, \quad \alpha = 5.0 \tag{11}$$

$$\text{Voltage violation: } e_{volt} = n_{viol}^{volt} \cdot \beta, \quad \beta = 0.001 \tag{12}$$

$$\text{Thermal violation: } e_{therm} = n_{viol}^{therm} \cdot \gamma, \quad \gamma = 0.002 \tag{13}$$

Where, α, β and γ are penalty factors that assign a proportional cost to each violation.

n_{viol}^{volt} denotes the count of buses violating the voltage constraints.

n_{viol}^{therm} denotes the number of branches experiencing current overloads.

Penalty factors were initially selected heuristically then validated through sensitivity analysis, and results show that +/-1 order of magnitude variations in penalty values yielded no significant shift in feasibility enforcement or Pareto-optimal solution quality. Penalty terms were also normalized relative to the magnitudes of the corresponding objective functions to prevent numerical imbalance between objectives and constraints. The foregoing measures conform to established practices in literature (Avvari & Kumar, 2022; Liang *et al.*, 2024).

All non-convergent solutions were dominated and systematically excluded from the Pareto-optimal set. The final penalized loss function was expressed as:

$$f_1^*(x) = f_1(x) + e_{volt} + e_{budget} + e_{therm} \tag{14}$$

This ensures that feasible solutions are prioritized while still allowing exploration of infeasible regions.

3.4 Optimization algorithms and implementation

Two algorithms, NSGA-II and its hybrid variant NSGA-II-HHO, were evaluated for multi-objective optimization. NSGA-II served as the benchmark/baseline owing to its status as the gold standard in evolutionary multi-objective optimization, with over 30,000 citations and proven robustness across engineering domains (Deb, Pratap, Agarwal, & Meyarivan, 2002; Verma, Pant, & Snasel, 2021). Both algorithms addressed a bi-objective formulation, minimizing feeder conductor losses and capital cost.

3.4.1 Chromosome encoding

The chromosome was encoded as a fixed-length integer vector representing conductor types assigned to each of the 32 branches in the IEEE 33-bus system. Each gene corresponds to a branch, with integer values 0 to ($K - 1$), denoting available conductor types ($K = 3$: 0-ACSR 1/0, 1-ACSR 2/0, 2-ACSR 3/0). Gene positions map directly to branch indices (e.g., index 0: bus 1–2, index 1: bus 2–3). NSGA-II employed

crowded tournament selection with non-dominated sorting (NDS) and crowding distance (CD) for Pareto diversity (Deb *et al.*, 2002). Variation was introduced via the *Uniform Integer Mutation* operator (mutUniformInt in DEAP), which randomly replaces genes with valid conductor indices at low probability, enhancing exploration and preventing premature convergence (Fortin, De Rainville, Gardner, Parizéau, & Gagné, 2012; Katoch, Chauhan, & Kumar 2021).

3.4.2 Common parameters, Computational Budget, Stopping Criterion, and Parameter Tuning

The configuration prioritized a fair and unbiased comparison. The chromosome was encoded as a string of integer, where each gene models a feeder segment and its allele model the selected conductor type, thus defining the whole IEEE 33-bus conductor layout. The bi-objective function co-optimizes real power loss (MW) and conductor CAPEX under the peak (40%), average (40%), and light (20%) loading scenarios. All constraint violations pertaining to budget, voltage, and thermal limits were penalized within the fitness function. In line with related studies (Zhao, Du, Tu, Ma, Shang, & Xiang, 2025), NDS and CD mechanisms enforced a balance between convergence and diversity, while two-point crossover and uniform integer mutation (probability 0.10 - 0.20) further ensured population diversity. Elitism was maintained through an external Pareto set that archives all non-dominated solutions across generations.

An identical computational budget for each algorithm was upheld for equitable assessment. The termination criterion was after 80 generations with a population size of 120, i.e., 9,600 function evaluations. NSGA-II-HHO integrated the HHO search dynamics within this fixed budget, so that performance gains arose only from hybridization rather than additional computational resources. Each experiment was iterated 20 times using different pseudo-random seeds, allowing cumulative performance tracking and minimizing single-run bias (Derrac, García, Molina, & Herrera, 2011; Agushaka, Ezugwu, & Abualigah, 2022). Evolutionary parameters shared by both algorithms included a crossover probability of 0.85, mutation probability of 0.20, NSGA-II-based selection, and the fixed computational budget. The HHO specific parameters include; $\beta = 1.5$ for Lévy flights, linear energy decay (2 to 0), strategy updates every 10 generations, and integer-bounded position encoding.

All parameters were validated through a preliminary sensitivity analysis on reduced instances to ensure stable convergence. NSGA-II-HHO inherited NSGA-

II settings without extra tuning, while HHO parameters remained as is. Consequently, performance differences between algorithms can therefore be confidently attributed to the hybridization strategy rather than a lopsided parameter configurations (Heidari, Mirjalili, Faris, Aljarah, Mafarja, & Chen, 2019; An, Zhang, & Shao, 2024).

3.4.3 Hybridization strategy

The NSGA-II-HHO hybrid employed a master-slave framework in which NSGA-II performs global exploration, while HHO provides periodic local intensification. NSGA-II maintained population diversity and Pareto dominance through crowded tournament selection, two-point crossover probability (CXPB), and uniform integer mutation probability (MUTPB). HHO was triggered every 10 generations, initializing with the best Pareto solution. Its energy-based mechanism guides the search behavior i.e., when $|E| \geq 1$, particles explore the solution space, while for $|E| < 1$, 1 of 4 exploitation strategies (soft/hard besiege with or without progressive dives) was applied (Heidari *et al.*, 2019; Tripathy, Reddy Maddikunta, Pham, Gadekallu, Dev, Pandya, & ElHalawany, 2022). Levy flights enhance local search diversity, and improved HHO solutions replace weaker GA individuals, thereby strengthening convergence while preserving elitism. This coordination helped to maintain exploration/exploitation balance, enhance convergence speed, and shore up quality solutions (Houssein, Hosney, Oliva, Mohamed, & Hassaballah, 2021).

Because conductor selection/allocation is a discrete optimization problem, HHO was constrained to operate in continuous space while ensuring that integer solutions remain feasible. Particle coordinates were kept updated and mapped to conductor indices via rounding and clamping before evaluation (to minimize search bias, a nearest-integer mapping with feasibility checks was done, and outputs were averaged over the different independent runs). Levy flights, besiege mechanisms and all movement strategies, had their continuous outputs discretized to preserve solution validity. Fitness evaluations were performed only on integer-converted coordinates, while local and global bests were stored in continuous format to facilitate the search dynamics (Emary, Zawbaa, & Hassanien, 2016).

3.4.3.1 Mathematical justification

(Deb *et al.*, 2002; Heidari *et al.*, 2019; Li *et al.*, 2022; Ma *et al.*, 2023; Sharma *et al.*, 2025;)

Restating the bi-objective problem:

$$\min_{x \in X} F(x) = [f_1(x), f_2(x)]^T \quad (15)$$

$$x \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

For the NSGA-II, the Pareto dominance partitions the population into ranked fronts:

$$x^* < x \Leftrightarrow (f_1(x^*) \leq f_1(x) \wedge f_2(x^*) \leq f_2(x)) \wedge (f_1(x^*) < f_1(x) \vee f_2(x^*) < f_2(x)) \quad (16)$$

This induces non-dominated fronts:

F_1 : Pareto-optimal set (rank $r = 1$)

F_k : solutions dominated by those in F_{k-1}

While the crowding distance maintains spread across the Pareto front:

$$\text{For solution } i: d_i = \frac{f_1^{(i+1)} - f_1^{(i-1)}}{f_1^{\max} - f_1^{\min}} + \frac{f_2^{(i+1)} - f_2^{(i-1)}}{f_2^{\max} - f_2^{\min}} \quad (17)$$

where:

d_i : crowding distance (density estimate)

$f_k^{(i \pm 1)}$: neighboring solutions in objective k (sorted order)

f_k^{\max}, f_k^{\min} : bounds of objective k

The tournament selection enforces the partial order:

$$x_i > x_j \Leftrightarrow r_i < r_j \vee (r_i = r_j \wedge d_i > d_j) \quad (18)$$

where: r_i is the Pareto rank (front index F_k)

For NSGA-II, genetic variation is random and isotropic in \mathbb{R}^n and independent of objective-space geometry.

Perturbations are stochastic with step size scaling:

$$\| \Delta x \| \sim \mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{t}) \quad (19)$$

i.e., diffusive search is inefficient for escaping local Pareto regions (slow basin escape)

For the HHO adaptive search kernel, escape energy decays as:

$$E = 2E_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{T}\right), E_0 \sim \mathcal{U}(-1, 1) \quad (20)$$

where, E controls exploration/exploitation, t is the iteration index and T is the maximum iterations.

For the Exploration phase ($|E| \geq 1$) i.e., random perch dispersal:

$$x(t+1) = x_{\text{rand}}(t) - r_1 |x_{\text{rand}}(t) - 2r_2 x(t)| \quad (21)$$

where, x_{rand} : randomly chosen solution and $r_1, r_2 \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$

For the Exploitation ($|E| < 1$) i.e., Lévy-enhanced besiege:

$$x(t+1) = \Delta x(t) + x_{\text{rabbitt}}(t) \cdot \text{LF}(\beta) \quad (22)$$

where, $\Delta x(t) = x_{\text{rabbitt}}(t) - x(t)$

x_{rabbitt} is the best attractor

where the Lévy flight step is drawn from:

$$\text{LF}(\beta) \sim \frac{u}{|v|^{1/\beta}}, u \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_u^2), v \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1) \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma_u = \left[\frac{\Gamma(1+\beta) \sin(\frac{\pi\beta}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{1+\beta}{2}) \beta \cdot 2^{(\beta-1)/2}} \right]^{1/\beta} \quad (24)$$

Where, $\beta \in (1, 2)$ is the Lévy index (heavy-tailed step distribution)

But HHO is inherently single-objective i.e., it has no Pareto dominance, no diversity mechanism, and converges to a single attractor x_{rabbitt} .

The hybrid operator

The NSGA-II's blind genetic step is replaced with HHO's energy-adaptive update, applied inside the dominance-ranked population. The rabbit attractor is redefined as the crowding-weighted Pareto-optimal centroid:

$$x_{\text{rabbitt}} = \arg \min_{x \in F_1} \| F(x) \|_2 \quad (25)$$

Where, F_1 : non-dominated front and $\| F(x) \|_2 = \sqrt{f_1(x)^2 + f_2(x)^2}$

The unified update becomes:

$$x_i^{(t+1)} = \Phi_{\text{HHO}}(x_i^{(t)}, x_{\text{rabbitt}}^{(t)}, E), x_i \in F_k \quad (26)$$

with the phase switch governed by:

$$x_i^{(t+1)} = \begin{cases} \text{Exploration update} & |E| \geq 1 \\ x_{\text{rabbitt}} - E |x_{\text{rabbitt}} - x_i^{(t)}| & \frac{1}{2} \leq |E| < 1 \\ \Delta x^{(t)} + x_{\text{rabbitt}} \cdot \text{LF}(\beta) & |E| < \frac{1}{2} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

Justification of synergy

Super-diffusive Convergence. Standard genetic mutation is a Gaussian random walk with mean-square displacement:

Gaussian mutation (diffusive, slow) :

$$(| \Delta x |^2)_{GA} \sim t \tag{28}$$

Lévy flights yield super-diffusion (faster traversal across disconnected Pareto segments):

$$(| \Delta x |^2)_{LF} \sim t^{2/\beta}, 1 < \beta < 2 \tag{29}$$

The two mechanisms act on orthogonal degrees of freedom: d_i (crowding) $\perp E(t)$ (energy) i.e., d_i ensures uniform coverage of the Pareto curve in R^2 and $E(t)$ controls search intensity in decision space

Neither operator interferes with the other, so diversity and exploitation are simultaneously optimized.

The hybrid's phase-switching probability balances global search and local refinement:

$$\Pr(\text{exploration}) = \Pr(| E | \geq 1), \tag{30}$$

$$\Pr(\text{exploitation}) = \Pr(| E | < 1) \tag{31}$$

NSGA-II contributes the multi-objective selection topology; HHO contributes the dynamically adaptive, landscape-sensitive search kernel.

The best HHO solution was injected into GA after conversion to integer format, so as to ensure seamless integration between modules. This adaptation facilitated HHO's energy-dependent exploration-exploitation balance, enable thorough search around elite solutions, and maintain feasibility within the discrete problem structure (Yousri, Allam, Eteiba, & Suganthan, 2020; Liu, Cai, Shi, Wang, Zhang, Li, & Cui, 2023). Figure 1 summarizes the NSGA-II-HHO hybridization strategy.

Figure 1: The NSGA-II-HHO flowchart (Global-Local Synergy).

3.4.4 Implementation environment

The Distributed Evolutionary Algorithms in Python (DEAP); an evolutionary optimization framework for NSGA-II operators was the implementation platform (Fortin *et al.*, 2012); extended with custom modules to support the integration of discrete HHO. Numerical computations were performed with NumPy, while pandas was used to facilitate the handling of structured data and post-processing (Harris *et al.*, 2020). All experiments were executed on a Windows 10 (64-bit) workstation featuring an Intel Core i7 CPU (3.2 GHz, 8 cores) with 16 GB RAM, and double-precision floating-point arithmetic.

3.5 Performance evaluation

Algorithm performance was evaluated using two main objectives i.e., feeder power loss minimization (MW) and conductor CAPEX minimization (USD); thus, realistically capturing the techno-economic priorities of distribution network planning (Sadiq & Antar, 2024). Solution quality was quantified using standard Pareto-front indicators such as Hypervolume (HV),

Inverted Generational Distance Plus (IGD⁺), Extent, Spacing, as well as runtime; providing complementary perspectives on convergence, diversity, and computational efficiency (Audet, Bibeon, Cartier, Le Digabel, & Salomon, 2021).

3.5.1 Reference front and normalization

Pairwise dominance was used to identify non-dominated solutions, where one solution dominates another when it is non-inferior in all objectives and clearly superior in at least one. A feasible-only front restricted to solutions satisfying all voltage, thermal, and budget constraints, was similarly derived, thus ensuring dominance within the feasible region (Fan *et al.*, 2019; Liang, Lin, Yue, Ban, & Yu, 2024). The resulting global reference points (Ishibuchi, Imada, Setoguchi, & Nojima, 2018; Niu, & Li, 2025). were: utopia (0.05187 MW, \$29,720) and nadir (0.0955 MW, \$43,703), expanded by 10% to (0.1050 MW, \$48,073) for HV and IGD⁺ evaluation.

3.6 Validation of load-flow solver accuracy

Figure 2: Validation of load-flow solver (Active (ΔP) and Reactive (ΔQ) power mismatches)

From Figure 2, it can be observed that the load flow solution demonstrated acceptable level of numerical accuracy, with both active (ΔP) and reactive (ΔQ) power mismatches across all buses remaining well below the 1×10^{-6} pu tolerance level. Such low mismatch levels are widely accepted as indicators of reliable and precise steady-state solutions in power system analysis (El-Fergany, 2025)

4.0 Results and Discussions

This is a sample text inserted for illustration of the Result and Discussion of the article and it is to be replaced with the Result and Discussion text of the article for submission. In this section, the author presents, comments, and interprets the data that has been collected in the research. It may include relevant subsections including Tables, Figures and Plates.

Across 20 independent runs, both algorithms consistently converged toward top quality Pareto fronts that effectively captured the bi-objective trade-off. Nonetheless, notable differences were observed

in convergence precision, solution diversity, and search dynamics. The following sections present and discuss the major findings obtained from the comparative analysis.

4.1 Performance metrics

From Figure. 3 and Table 1, the only clear

performance distinction is in IGD+, where NSGA-II-HHO performs significantly better, supported by a moderate effect size and a positive median shift. For runtime, there is a weak, non-significant evidence that NSGA-II may be faster, with a moderate effect and notable median reduction. All other metrics indicate comparable performance i.e., no diversity loss in NSGA-II-HHO.

Figure 3: Violin plots of the performance metrics (Extent, HV, IGD+, Pareto-optimal solution, Runtime and Spacing)

The observed trends in Figure 3 are quantitatively reinforced in Table 1.

Table 1: Statistical analysis

Performance Metric	NSGA-II Median [IQR]	NSGA-II-HHO Median [IQR]	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Effect Size (r) [95% CI]	Hodges-Lehmann Median Difference [95% CI]
HV	0.8681 [0.0059]	0.8682 [0.0070]	178	0.561	-0.11 [-0.39, 0.19]	-0.0009 [-0.0038, 0.0020]
IGD	0.0039 [0.0026]	0.0022 [0.0018]	286	0.021	0.43 [0.15, 0.64]	0.0013 [0.0003, 0.0025]
SPACING	0.0142 [0.0018]	0.0137 [0.0026]	220	0.598	0.10 [-0.20, 0.39]	0.0002 [-0.0009, 0.0118]
EXTENT	1.0529 [0.0435]	1.0728 [0.0477]	142	0.119	-0.29 [-0.54, 0.01]	-0.0059 [-0.0329, 0.0003]
OPTIMAL SOLUTION	48.0 [4.5]	48.0 [5.25]	190.5	0.807	-0.048 [-0.34, 0.25]	0.0 [-3.0, 2.0]
RUNTIME	4947.6 [2429.4]	5415.8 [1730.7]	133	0.072	-0.34 [-0.57, -0.04]	-603.2 [-993.4, 58.7]

4.1.1 Computational Cost (Runtime) Analysis

As is common in similar studies (Ma *et al.*, 2023; Soni *et al.*, 2024), the hybrid algorithm - due to computational complexity - is almost 10% slower than the NSGA-II algorithm (median runtime of 5415.8 s vs. 4947.6 s). While there is a moderate effect size (r

= -0.34) and a delay of about 603 seconds, the difference is not statistically significant (p = 0.072). The fact that the confidence interval crosses zero suggests that there is a runtime overhead but statistically marginal,

These quantitative observations are further corroborated by the Pareto front distributions and convergence evolution trends shown in Figures. 4 and 5.

4.2 Pareto front analysis

The Pareto front visualization in Figure. 4 fully supports the statistical findings and reveals the fact that the NSGA-II-HHO hybrid produces a less dispersed distribution of solutions along the trade-off curve. Together with the 43.59% reduction in IGD^+ , there is good ground to conclude that the hybrid achieves solutions closer to the global optimal set for this test MOOP.

Similar exploration capabilities may also be observed from Figure 4 since within the \$30,000–\$40,000 cost and 0.052–0.087 MW loss range, both algorithms provided comparable coverage of the objective space.

Figure 4: Pareto front plots

4.3 Convergence evolution analysis

The convergence evolution plot of Figure. 5 presents the significant influence of hybridization on the dynamic search behavior of both algorithms from generation to generation. During the early phase (0 - 20 generations), NSGA-II and NSGA-II-HHO both display similar rapid expansion of Pareto-optimal solutions. However, between generations 20 - 50, the hybrid shows a notably steeper convergence trend, demonstrating sustained rise in solution quality. By the final phase (50 - 80), both algorithms are observed to stabilize, with NSGA-II-HHO achieving a higher density of Pareto-optimal solutions that supports the 43.59% improvement in IGD^+ .

4.4 Run to run variability analysis

However, NSGA-II-HHO may also be observed to generate a smoother and more continuous Pareto front, particularly around the critical knee region (\$30,000–\$34,000); reflecting a better balance between cost and loss. Subject to comprehensive multi-scenario validation, the hybrid therefore can be viewed as a tool with the potentials of facilitating a more reliable trade-off assessment as well as precise conductor selection and assignment, thereby reducing the probability of post-installation adjustments.

Further, both algorithms consistently map out comparable decision regions; indicating coherent search of the decision space. However, the hybrid may be observed to demonstrate stronger intra-cluster exploitation, producing solutions that are closer to the true Pareto front. Potentially, a greater decision reliability and computational efficiency is therefore expected

Figure 5: Convergence evolution plots

Moreover, the hybrid's convergence behavior appears to be characterized by fewer stagnation intervals and tighter clustering across independent runs; a notable sign of greater reliability. Also, its enhanced mid-phase trajectory tends to guide the search process better toward the true Pareto front, suggesting a higher-quality solution with better distribution.

Within the limits of the results obtained from the test case used in this study, the hybrid exhibits potentials for more consistent identification of optimal conductor configurations, balanced trade-offs between cost and loss as well as reduced computational uncertainty in distribution network planning. This however comes at the cost of no practically relevant improvement in divergence.

Figure 6: Run-to-run variability analysis

The influence of hybridization is examined further in Figure 6. The left plot shows that both NSGA-II (pink) and NSGA-II-HHO (gold) achieve nearly the same mean power loss values, hovering within 0.057–0.060 MW; with observable lower values being recorded more by the hybrid with notably greater consistency. However, the wider shaded region associated with NSGA-II suggests higher run-to-run variability.

In contrast, the right plot presents the NSGA-II as consistent at producing slightly lower mean CAPEX, (around \$34,000) compared to NSGA-II-HHO, which appears to stabilize between \$34,500 and \$35,000. Despite the hybrid’s reduced variability, this improvement in stability appears to come at the expense of marginally higher mean conductor CAPEX; suggesting a trade-off between optimality and reliability.

The HHO component thus acts as a stabilizer, mitigating stochasticity and enhancing reliability with minimal compromise in overall performance. These benefits are accompanied by acceptable increases in CAPEX and runtime. Overall, Figure 6 shows that

hybridization shifts the optimization focus toward consistency and reproducibility rather than absolute optimality. Practically, the reduced stochasticity ensures reliable conductor selection and assignment in distribution network planning; yielding reproducible cost vs loss trade-offs under varying computational conditions. The hybrid’s inability to excel in exploring the extremes of the entire solution space stands as its major shortcoming.

4.5 Financial budget utilization performance

The histogram and consistency plots of Fig 7 and 8 demonstrate that hybridizing NSGA-II with HHO increases budget utilization to more consistent levels across optimization runs. While NSGA-II-HHO concentrates solutions in the 90 - 96 % utilization range, the NSGA-II does same but at a lower 86 - 90 % range; indicating that the hybrid assumes a fuller utilization of the budgeted investment capacity. The prevalence of lower mean losses and the rarity of low budget utilization outcomes further highlight the hybrid algorithm’s ability to yield lower loss solutions that remain within the financial budget.

Figure 7: Budget utilization

Figure 8: CV of budget utilization

A minor trade-off, however, is observed in terms of the consistency in budget utilization. As observed in Fig. 8, the coefficient of variation (CV) analysis reveals that NSGA-II maintains a slightly lower median CV (approx. 8.0 %) compared to NSGA-II-

HHO (approx. 8.4 %), with a narrower interquartile range, suggesting marginally greater stability in budget use across independent runs. The hybrid tends to prefer a slightly higher average budget utilization, as well as a slightly broader CV spread (≈ 7.8 - 8.9 %),

implying modestly higher variability in the budget use. Such a trade-off is common in hybrid metaheuristics, where the introduction of additional intensification mechanisms improves global search performance but may incur acceptable fluctuations in convergence with respect to individual objectives. (Najm, Khaleel, Hamed, & Ahmed, 2024; Tu, Wang, Huo, & Wang, 2023; Vadi, Bildirici, & Kaplan, 2025).

From the practical perspective of the context depicted by the test case in this study, the higher budget utilization associated with NSGA-II-HHO is justified when the additional capital investment translates to significant long-term gains in loss reduction and operational efficiency. These solutions lie in choice regions of the Pareto front, and are potential tools for facilitating decision-making goals that emphasize lifecycle cost minimization and enhanced system performance rather than strict minimization of individual objectives in the short term.

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5.0 Conclusion

Within the limits of the network topology and the underlying mathematical structure/design of this study's test case, the hybrid NSGA-II-HHO approach clearly improves the reliability, precision, and efficiency of distribution network planning by enhancing convergence toward the true Pareto front and significantly reducing the overall solution variability. This promises a more consistent and reproducible conductor allocation, so that repeated optimization runs may become unnecessary. Exploration capability and diversity is preserved but not significantly improved, while producing smoother and more interpretable Pareto fronts, thus enabling more reliable cost vs loss trade-off analysis. Although it suffers from a marginal increase in mean conductor CAPEX, greater spread in budget utilization, and a modest rise in computational time, these drawbacks are surpassed by the considerable gains in overall solution stability and decision confidence. In sum, the hybridization refines the standard NSGA-II search process by prioritizing convergence quality, robustness, and economic relevance rather than strict financial cost minimization in the short term. The

primary merit of the study which is the statistically significant improvement in IGD⁺ with no significant loss in other investigated performance metrics, highlights the hybrid's potentials to excel in similar contexts in real-world distribution network optimization under uncertainty.

Future work will consider larger test systems (e.g., 69 and 118-bus networks) to extensively validate scalability and computational complexity. Uncertainty will be integrated through stochastic load modeling, scenario generation and DG variability; with the MOOP reformulated to fully account for expected performance and constraint violation. The hybrid algorithm will be further finetuned through local search integration and adaptive parameter control, benchmarked systematically against other hybrid metaheuristics. Validation on real feeder datasets will employ techno-economic and reliability indices; and computational efficiency will be addressed through parallelization and GPU-based implementation to support large-scale, real-time deployment.

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